

TERPENOID. PART III. A NOVEL SYNTHESIS OF *dl*-PHELLANDRAL

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An elegant new synthesis of *dl*-phellandral has been achieved by adopting the method of Seifert and Schinz for the creation of an $\alpha\beta$ -double bond in a cyclohexane aldehyde system.

Phellandral, an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated aldehydic terpene, occurs in several essential oils (Simonsen, "The Terpenes", 1947, Vol. I, p. 308) in *laevo* as well as in *dextro* form. The constitution of phellandral was largely determined by the oxidative studies of Burger and Macbeth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 145). Phellandric acid, obtained by silver oxide oxidation of phellandral, followed by hydrogenation, was identified with hexahydrocuminic acid (Cooke *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1940, 808). These authors also synthesised *dl*-phellandric acid by dehydrohalogenation of α -bromohexahydrocuminic acid. Frank *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3889) reported a synthesis of *dl*-phellandral via *dl*-phellandric acid. The latter was resolved by these authors and the *d*-form identified with the optically active acid obtained from the natural *d*-aldehyde. The synthesis by Frank *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), comprising eleven steps, had other limitations as well. For instance, it was difficult to obtain pure phellandric acid which was invariably contaminated with the $\beta\gamma$ -isomer. Moreover, the overall yield of phellandral, starting from *p*-cuminol, was very low (about 6%). Recently, another synthesis of *dl*-phellandral has been described by Gillespie *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 665). In this, 1-vinyl-4-isopropylcyclohexanol was ozonised and the resulting hydroxy-aldehyde, when treated with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone in alcoholic sulphuric acid, underwent dehydration *in situ* to furnish the dinitrophenylhydrazone of *dl*-phellandral from which the aldehyde was regenerated by treatment with pyruvic acid.

We have now evolved a method of synthesis of *dl*-phellandral (IV), which is very much simpler compared to both these methods, and it affords the terpene aldehyde in an overall yield of about 18%, starting from 3-isopropylcyclohex-2-enone. Seifert and Schinz (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1951, 34, 728) prepared 3-methylcyclohexene-1-aldehyde by lithium aluminium hydride reduction of 2-methyl-6-isobutoxymethylene-cyclohexanone, followed by decomposition of the reduced product with a strong acid.

We extended this reaction sequence to 2-isobutoxymethylene-5-isopropylcyclohexanone (II), when a 64% yield of *dl*-phellandral (IV) was obtained.

The decomposition of the reduced product, such as (III), with acid to an unsaturated aldehyde, such as (IV), was explained by Seifert and Schinz (*loc. cit.*) as an anionotropic rearrangement. But as the reaction takes place under strongly acidic condition, this can be explained on the basis of the following sequences as well.

3-*iso*Propylcyclohexanone, the starting material in the present synthesis, was earlier prepared by Whitmore and Pedlow (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 758) by the action of *isopropylmagnesium chloride* on *cyclohex-2-enone*. But we preferred a different but more convenient route, comprising catalytic reduction of 3-*isopropylcyclohex-2-enone* (Birch and Mukherji, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2531) in presence of palladium-charcoal (5%). It was then formylated with ethyl formate under the condition prescribed by Johnson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 218) to obtain the formyl derivative (I). The structure of (I) is based on analogy with carbethoxylation of 3-methylcyclohexanone (Kötz and Hesse, *Annalen*, 1905, **342**, 306; cf. Part II, this issue, p. 853). The formyl derivative (I) was then refluxed with a mixture of *isobutanol*, benzene and a little *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (cf. Seifert and Schinz, *loc. cit.*), when 2-*isobutoxy*methylene-5-*isopropylcyclohexanone* (II) was produced in 41% yield.

The ultraviolet absorption spectra of the synthetic aldehyde (IV), $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$, 229 m μ (log ϵ , 4.1) and of its semicarbazone, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$, 262 m μ (log ϵ , 4.34) corresponded with those reported for natural *l*-plicliandral by Cooke and Macbeth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1408) and Evans and Gillam (*ibid.*, 1943, 565).

* E X P E R I M E N T A L

3-*iso*Propylcyclohexanone.—3-*iso*Propylcyclohex-2-enone (Birch and Mukherji, *loc. cit.*) (22 g.) in alcohol (200 c.c.) was shaken under hydrogen in presence of palladium-charcoal (5%, 2.2 g.) till one mole of hydrogen was taken up. After working up in the usual way, 21 g. (95%) of 3-*isopropylcyclohexanone* was obtained, b. p. 90-94°/8 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4631.

The semicarbazone, prepared quantitatively from the above ketone, was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 190° (Whitmore and Pedlow, *loc. cit.*, report m. p. 189-90°). (Found: N, 21.4. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{16}ON_3$: N, 21.52 per cent.)

2-*Hydroxymethylene-5-methylcyclohexanone* (I).—To a well-cooled suspension of sodium ethoxide (prepared from 4 g. of finely powdered sodium) in dry benzene (175 c.c.) was added slowly, with constant shaking, ethyl formate (13 g.) and the

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses by Drs. Strauss and Weiler, Oxford.

contents allowed to stand for about 2 hours. 3-*iso*Propylcyclohexanone (25 g.) in dry benzene (20 c.c.) was then added dropwise with swirling. The reaction mixture was then kept in a refrigerator for 24 hours and the solid mass was decomposed with ice-water. The aqueous layer was separated and acidified with iced HCl. The oily product was twice extracted with ether and the combined ethereal extract washed free of acid. After removal of the solvent the residual oil on distillation under reduced pressure came over at $135^{\circ}\text{--}140^{\circ}/12$ mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4922; yield 21 g. (71%). (Found: C, 71.48; H, 9.71. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 71.39; H, 9.59 per cent). It gave an intense violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution.

2-*isobutoxymethylene-5-isopropylcyclohexanone* (II).—A mixture of the above hydroxymethylene derivative (I: 20 g.), *isobutyl* alcohol (13.5 g.), dry benzene (125 c.c.) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (100 mg.) was refluxed in an oil-bath (120°) under a Dean and Stark water separator till no more water had separated. The cooled reaction mixture was diluted with water and the benzene layer washed with dilute alkali to remove *p*-toluenesulphonic acid and unchanged (I). The organic layer was then dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation yielded 11 g. (41%) of (II), b.p. $185^{\circ}\text{--}190^{\circ}/8$ mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4728. (Found: C, 74.55; H, 11.19. $C_{14}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 74.95; H, 10.78 per cent).

dl-Phellandral (IV).—To a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (1.56 g.) in absolute ether (150 c.c.) was added with mechanical stirring 2-*isobutoxymethylene-5-methylcyclohexanone* (II: 10 g.) in absolute ether (20 c.c.) at such a rate as to produce a gentle reflux. After the addition the reaction mixture was refluxed for another 15 minutes and then cooled to 10° . To this was then added dropwise, the temperature being kept below 0° , a well-cooled solution of H_2SO_4 (conc., 40 c.c.), ice (30 g.) and water (10 c.c.). Stirring was continued for one hour more and then the reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract, after being washed with sodium bicarbonate and water, was dried (Na_2SO_4) and fractionated when 4.3 g. (64%) of (IV) was obtained, b.p. $110^{\circ}\text{--}115^{\circ}/7\text{--}8$ mm. (Found: C, 79.12; H, 10.61. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{16}O$: C, 78.89; H, 10.59 per cent). n_D^{20} , 1.4885 (Frank *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report n_D^{20} 1.4869); λ_{max}^{210} , 229 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.1) (Cooke and Macbeth, *loc. cit.*, report for *l*-phellandral, λ_{max}^{210} , 228.5 $m\mu$; $\log \epsilon$, 4.27).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $203\text{--}204^{\circ}$ (Berry, Macbeth and Swanson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1448, report m.p. 200° for the *d*-phellandral derivative; Iskenderov, *Chem. Abst.*, 1938, 32, 126, records m.p. 204°). (Found: N, 20.00. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{18}ON_3$: N, 20.10 per cent). λ_{max}^{210} , 262 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.34) (Evans and Gillam, *loc. cit.*, reported for *l*-phellandral semicarbazone, λ_{max}^{210} , 265 $m\mu$; $\log \epsilon$, 4.18).

The 2-*4-dinitrophenylhydrazones* was prepared by the sulphuric acid method and was crystallised as red microcrystals from ethyl acetate, m.p. 204° (Berry, Macbeth and Swanson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1449, reported for *d*-phellandral-2-*4*-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 204°). (Found: N, 16.70. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_4$: N 16.86 per cent).

The oxime was prepared according to the directions of Fuson and Shriner ("Identification of Organic Compounds", John Wiley, 1948, p. 202) and was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 87° (Iskenderov, *loc. cit.*, reported m.p. 87.8°). (Found: N, 8.15. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{11}ON$: N, 8.15 per cent).

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